

When Teachers Become School Heads: Administrative and Instructional Competence of Teachers-in-Charge and Their Relationship to Students' Academic Performance

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Article Details:

Received: 10 April 2026

Revised: 19 April 2026

Accepted: 25 April 2026

Published: 8 May 2026

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Recommended Citation:

Martirez, L. N., Orbista, J. R. (2026). When Teachers Become School Heads: Administrative and Instructional Competence of Teachers-In-Charge and Their Relationship to Students' Academic Performance. *The International Review of Multidisciplinary Research*. 1 (5), 157-166 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20080524>

Index Terms:

teachers-in-charge, instructional leadership, administrative leadership, academic performance, public school teacher, teacher-leader duality

Abstract. This study examined the administrative and instructional leadership competence of Teachers-in-Charge (TICs) assigned at the primary grade level and investigated their relationship with pupils' academic performance in selected public schools in the Schools Division of Aklan, Philippines. A descriptive–correlational research design was employed involving 30 Teachers-in-Charge from the districts of Madalag and Libacao. Data were collected using a validated survey instrument measuring administrative leadership competence across personal, administrative, and creative skills and instructional leadership competence across supervision, curriculum monitoring, professional development support, instructional resource management, protection of instructional time, and student progress monitoring. Pupils' academic performance was measured using class mean final grades for School Year 2024–2025. Descriptive statistics and Pearson's Product–Moment Correlation Coefficient were used for data analysis. Findings revealed that Teachers-in-Charge demonstrated a high level of administrative leadership competence and instructional leadership competence. Learners under their supervision achieved an overall Very Satisfactory level of academic performance. However, results showed no statistically significant relationship between administrative leadership competence and pupils' academic performance and between instructional leadership competence and pupils' academic performance. The findings suggest that while Teachers-in-Charge demonstrate strong leadership competence necessary to sustain school operations and instructional processes, leadership competence alone may not directly predict learners' academic achievement in geographically isolated school contexts. External variables such as instructional resources, teacher workload, and learner-related factors may influence academic outcomes. The study highlights the importance of strengthening leadership preparation programs and institutional support systems for Teachers-in-Charge and provides empirical evidence to inform policy decisions related to school leadership deployment in underserved educational settings.

Introduction

Educational leadership plays a crucial role in ensuring the effective functioning of schools and improving student learning outcomes. However, when individuals are required to perform dual roles simultaneously, particularly teaching and school leadership responsibilities, the demands can become complex and challenging. Balancing instructional duties with administrative functions often results in increased workload, divided attention, and role strain that may affect both leadership effectiveness and classroom performance. In the context of basic education systems, particularly in developing educational settings, such situations commonly arise when leadership vacancies exist in schools.

In the Philippine educational system, school heads serve as key agents of instructional supervision and administrative management. Pursuant to Section 6.1 of the Implementing Rules and Regulations of Republic Act No. 9155, every public elementary and secondary school—or cluster of schools—must be led by a school head responsible for both administrative

and instructional leadership. However, due to shortages of qualified principals and head teachers in several school divisions, including the Division of Aklan, teachers are often designated as Teachers-in-Charge (TICs) to assume school leadership responsibilities in addition to their teaching duties. While this arrangement ensures continuity of school operations, it also creates additional demands that may affect leadership performance and instructional delivery.

Leadership effectiveness in schools has consistently been identified as one of the most influential factors contributing to improved student achievement, second only to classroom instruction (The Wallace Foundation, 2013). School leaders are expected to manage personnel, oversee curriculum implementation, support teachers' professional development, and ensure efficient utilization of school resources. These responsibilities become particularly challenging for Teachers-in-Charge who may lack formal preparation in school leadership or sufficient teaching experience prior to assuming administrative roles.

Educational management involves systematic planning, organizing, directing, and controlling school resources to achieve institutional goals efficiently and effectively (Bush, 2011; Chuaungo, 2015). In situations where newly hired or less experienced teachers are assigned as Teachers-in-Charge, gaps in leadership preparation may affect both administrative coordination and instructional supervision. As a result, the effectiveness of school operations and the academic performance of learners may be influenced by the leadership competencies demonstrated by these temporary school heads (Llego, 2019).

Despite the significant responsibilities assigned to Teachers-in-Charge, existing literature has largely focused on their lived experiences, role challenges, and coping mechanisms rather than examining their leadership competence in relation to learners' academic outcomes. Limited empirical evidence exists regarding how the administrative and instructional leadership performance of Teachers-in-Charge relates to student achievement, particularly in primary education contexts. Addressing this gap is essential for informing leadership development initiatives and policy decisions related to school head deployment in underserved schools.

Thus, this study investigates the administrative and instructional leadership competence of Teachers-in-Charge assigned at the primary grade level and examines their relationship with pupils' academic performance. Findings from this study are expected to contribute to strengthening leadership preparation programs, improving school management practices, and supporting evidence-based decision-making within the Department of Education

Research Questions

1.) What is the level of administrative leadership competence of Teachers-in-Charge assigned at the primary grade level in terms of: a. personal skills; b. administrative leadership skills; and c. creative skills?; 2) What is the level of instructional leadership competence of Teachers-in-Charge assigned at the primary grade level?; 3) What is the level of pupils' academic performance under Teachers-in-Charge assigned at the primary grade level?; and 4) Is there a significant relationship between the administrative and instructional leadership competence of Teachers-in-Charge and pupils' academic performance?

Assumptions of the Study

This study is anchored on certain fundamental premises that are accepted as true and valid to establish the foundation of the research. It is assumed that Teachers-in-Charge are fully knowledgeable and aware of their dual responsibilities as classroom teachers and school leaders, and that they are expected to possess and demonstrate the required administrative and instructional competence as defined by existing Department of Education policies, standards, and guidelines. It is also presumed that the indicators and criteria used to measure their level of competence in terms of managing school operations, implementing programs, supervising instruction, and leading academic activities are relevant, appropriate, and reliable standards for assessing their performance and capability.

Furthermore, the study assumes that the respondents will provide honest, accurate, and sincere responses to the research instruments based on their actual experiences, practices, and true level of capacity in performing their duties, as there are no right or wrong answers to the items being asked. Similarly, it is taken for granted that the data gathered regarding students' academic performance, which are sourced from official school records and documents, are complete, correct, and reliable representations of the learners' academic achievement and progress, serving as valid measures of educational outcomes.

It is also assumed that the administrative and instructional competence of Teachers-in-Charge are significant factors that directly or indirectly influence the quality of school management, the effectiveness of teaching and learning processes, and the overall academic success of students. While recognizing that there are other factors that may affect student

performance, this study assumes that these external variables remain constant or have minimal influence that does not significantly alter or invalidate the relationship being examined in this research. Lastly, it is presumed that the conditions, working environment, and circumstances of the schools included in this study are representative and comparable to similar educational settings, making the findings and conclusions applicable and relevant to other schools managed by Teachers-in-Charge.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive–correlational research design to examine the relationship between the administrative and instructional leadership performance of Teachers-in-Charge (TICs) and pupils’ academic performance. Descriptive–correlational designs are appropriate for investigating the direction and magnitude of relationships among variables without manipulating them, allowing researchers to describe existing conditions and determine whether statistically significant associations exist between variables (Devi et al., 2023).

In the present study, the descriptive component was used to determine the level of administrative and instructional leadership performance of Teachers-in-Charge assigned at the primary grade level, while the correlational component examined the relationship between leadership performance and pupils’ academic achievement. This approach enabled the researcher to analyze naturally occurring variations in leadership practices and identify patterns of association between leadership performance and academic achievement in schools led by Teachers-in-Charge.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study consisted of 30 Teachers-in-Charge assigned to public schools in the Districts of Madalag and Libacao, Schools Division of Aklan. These respondents simultaneously performed instructional responsibilities as classroom teachers and administrative responsibilities as acting school heads.

A complete enumeration sampling technique was employed, whereby all Teachers-in-Charge were selected as respondents. This sampling method was appropriate because the target population was relatively small and accessible, allowing the study to capture the perspectives of the entire group of Teachers-in-Charge within the identified districts.

Of the 30 respondents, 17 were assigned in Madalag District and 13 in Libacao District. On average, the respondents had served as Teachers-in-Charge for approximately seven years, indicating substantial experience in managing both instructional and administrative responsibilities in geographically isolated schools. Identification and confirmation of respondents were conducted through coordination with district offices and school administrators. A structured listing process supported by an online confirmation form ensured that all eligible Teachers-in-Charge were included in the study.

Research Instrument

Data were collected using a survey instrument entitled the Administrative and Instructional Leadership Competence Instrument for Teachers-in-Charge (see appendix B), which was adapted from previously validated leadership assessment tools. The instrument consisted of three parts: 1) Respondents’ Profile - This section collected demographic and professional information, including age, sex, years of teaching experience, highest educational attainment, and grade level handled. These variables were used to describe the characteristics of the respondents; 2) Administrative Leadership Competence Scale - This section measured administrative leadership competence across three domains: personal skills, administrative skills, and creative skills. Each domain consisted of ten indicators rated using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 5 (Strongly Agree) to 1 (Strongly Disagree); 3) Instructional Leadership Competence Scale - This section measured instructional leadership practices using 40 indicators covering: instructional supervision, curriculum monitoring, professional development support, protection of instructional time, classroom observation practices, instructional resource management, and student progress monitoring. Responses were measured using the same five-point Likert scale.

In addition to the survey instrument, students’ academic performance served as an outcome variable. The final grades of pupils from 30 classes handled by the Teachers-in-Charge during School Year 2024–2025 were collected and averaged to represent class-level academic performance.

The instrument underwent content validation by the research adviser and three experts in educational research and leadership to ensure alignment with the objectives of the study. Peer debriefing was also conducted to improve clarity and coherence of the questionnaire items.

Following expert validation, pilot testing and member checking were conducted among individuals with characteristics like the study respondents to ensure clarity, cultural appropriateness, and interpretability of the items. Suggestions from validators were incorporated prior to final administration of the instrument.

Data Gathering Procedure and Analysis

Prior to data collection, formal permission was obtained (see appendix a). After approval was secured, the researcher coordinated with the identified respondents regarding the administration schedule of the survey instruments. Data collection was conducted through both online and paper-based survey administration, depending on respondents' accessibility and preference. Respondents were oriented regarding the objectives of the study, confidentiality procedures, and voluntary nature of participation prior to answering the questionnaire. Survey responses were collected using structured Likert-scale instruments to measure administrative and instructional leadership competence. In addition, pupils' final grades for School Year 2024–2025 were obtained with approval from school authorities and in compliance with institutional data privacy policies. To ensure consistency in administration procedures, identical instructions and instruments were used across all respondents. Collected responses were encoded and prepared for statistical analysis.

Descriptive and inferential statistical techniques were employed to analyze the collected data. Descriptive statistics, specifically mean and standard deviation, were used to determine the level of administrative and instructional leadership performance of Teachers-in-Charge and to summarize pupils' academic performance. Prior to inferential testing, assumptions of normality were examined and determined to be satisfied. Although Likert-scale responses are ordinal in nature, aggregated composite scores were treated as approximately interval data, which is an accepted practice in educational research.

To determine the relationship between variables, Pearson's Product–Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson's r) was used to examine the strength and direction of relationships between administrative leadership performance, instructional leadership performance, and pupils' academic performance. The level of statistical significance was set a priori at $\alpha = .05$.

Leadership performance scores were interpreted using the following scale:

Range	Interpretation
4.21–5.00	Very High
3.41–4.20	High
2.61–3.40	Moderate
1.81–2.60	Low
1.00–1.80	Very Low

Pupils' academic performance was interpreted following the grading descriptors prescribed in Department of Education Order No. 8, s. 2015. Correlation strength was interpreted using standard guidelines for Pearson's r coefficients (Ullah, 2024).

Results and Discussion

Level of Administrative Leadership Competence of Teachers in Charge

Table 1 presents the level of administrative leadership competence of Teachers-in-Charge in terms of administrative personal skills, administrative leadership competence, and administrative creativity skills. The results indicate that Teachers-in-Charge demonstrated a high level of administrative leadership competence overall ($M = 3.60$, $SD = 0.33$).

Among the three indicators, administrative leadership competence obtained the highest mean ($M = 3.71$, $SD = 0.29$), followed by administrative personal skills ($M = 3.57$, $SD = 0.32$), and administrative creativity skills ($M = 3.50$, $SD = 0.37$). All indicators fall within the high-level interpretation, suggesting that Teachers-in-Charge are generally capable of performing administrative responsibilities effectively despite their concurrent instructional roles.

The high level of administrative leadership competence indicates that Teachers-in-Charge possess the necessary interpersonal, managerial, and organizational skills required to supervise school operations, coordinate activities, and support teaching–learning processes even in geographically isolated school settings. This finding suggests that Teachers-in-Charge are able to adapt to leadership demands and maintain operational efficiency in schools despite the absence of formally designated school heads.

This result supports the assertion that effective school leadership is not limited to formally appointed principals but may also be demonstrated by teachers assigned leadership responsibilities when provided with opportunities to exercise administrative functions. According to The Wallace Foundation (2013), leadership practices that focus on organization, coordination, and instructional support significantly contribute to improved school functioning and student learning outcomes. Similarly, Hallinger (2011) emphasized that instructional and administrative leadership behaviors play a critical role in shaping school effectiveness, particularly in resource-constrained environments. The relatively lower mean obtained by administrative creativity skills, although still interpreted as high, suggests that Teachers-in-Charge may experience limitations in initiating innovative administrative strategies due to contextual constraints such as limited resources, geographic isolation, and workload demands associated with their dual roles. This observation aligns with Leithwood et al. (2008), who noted that leadership effectiveness in schools is influenced not only by leadership competence but also by contextual and structural conditions affecting decision-making opportunities.

The findings further support previous studies indicating that Teachers-in-Charge are capable of performing administrative functions effectively despite limited formal leadership preparation. For instance, Llego (2019) reported that Teachers-in-Charge frequently assume responsibilities such as supervising teachers, managing school programs, and coordinating instructional implementation in the absence of school heads. Likewise, Bush (2011) emphasized that leadership competence involves the ability to organize resources efficiently and support collaborative school processes regardless of formal designation.

The findings imply that Teachers-in-Charge in upland and geographically isolated schools demonstrate strong administrative leadership competence necessary for sustaining school operations despite the absence of permanent school heads. However, the slightly lower rating in administrative creativity skills suggests a need for enhanced leadership development programs focusing on innovation, decision-making autonomy, and strategic planning.

Variable	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Administrative Personal Skills	3.57	0.32	High
Administrative Leadership Competence	3.71	0.29	High
Administrative Creativity Skills	3.50	0.37	High
Overall Mean	3.60	0.33	High

Note: Scale – 4.21-5.00 (Very High), 3.41-4.20 (High), 2.61-3.40 (Moderate), 1.81-2.60 (Low), 1.00-1.80 (Very Low)

Table 1. Level of Administrative Leadership Competence of Teachers in Charge

Level of Instructional Leadership Competence of Teachers-in-Charge

Table 2 shows the level of instructional leadership competence of Teachers-in-Charge across key instructional leadership practices related to instructional resource management, classroom supervision, professional development support, protection of instructional time, monitoring of student progress, and curriculum implementation. The results reveal that Teachers-in-Charge demonstrated an overall high level of instructional leadership competence (M = 3.71, SD = 0.17).

Among the indicators, the highest-rated practices included encouraging teachers to use instructional materials freely (M = 3.90, SD = 0.31), encouraging teachers to engage students in classroom activities (M = 3.90, SD = 0.31), ensuring student attendance during class time (M = 3.87, SD = 0.35), encouraging teachers to come to class prepared and on time (M = 3.87, SD = 0.35), and communicating students' performance during parent-teacher meetings (M = 3.87, SD = 0.35). These findings suggest that Teachers-in-Charge actively support instructional delivery, maintain classroom engagement, and promote accountability among teachers and learners despite their concurrent administrative responsibilities.

The consistently high ratings across most indicators indicate that Teachers-in-Charge effectively perform their instructional leadership roles in supervising teaching-learning processes, supporting professional growth among teachers, and monitoring curriculum implementation. These leadership behaviors reflect the essential functions of instructional leadership, which emphasize improving teaching quality and strengthening student learning outcomes through supervision, collaboration, and curriculum monitoring. According to Philip Hallinger (2011), instructional leadership practices such as monitoring classroom instruction, supporting teacher development, and protecting instructional time are among the most significant contributors to school effectiveness.

Notably, the indicator "use class time of teachers for regular meetings" obtained a moderate rating (M = 2.90, SD = 1.09), which differs from the otherwise consistently high ratings across the instructional leadership dimensions. This finding suggests that Teachers-in-Charge generally avoid interrupting instructional time for administrative meetings, thereby

prioritizing classroom instruction. Protecting instructional time is widely recognized as a critical instructional leadership responsibility that supports improved learning conditions and academic achievement (Leithwood et al., 2008).

The high ratings obtained in indicators related to professional development support, instructional supervision, and curriculum monitoring further indicate that Teachers-in-Charge actively facilitate collaborative instructional improvement within their schools. These findings are consistent with research showing that instructional leaders who promote teacher collaboration and continuous professional learning contribute positively to instructional quality and student performance (Robinson et al., 2008).

Additionally, Teachers-in-Charge demonstrated strong leadership practices in monitoring student progress and communicating student performance to parents, highlighting their role in strengthening school-community partnerships that support learners' academic development. Effective engagement with teachers and parents has been identified as a key component of instructional leadership that enhances student achievement outcomes (Hallinger, 2011).

Overall, the findings suggest that Teachers-in-Charge are able to sustain effective instructional leadership practices despite the demands of their dual administrative and teaching responsibilities. Their capacity to support instructional processes reflects adaptability and commitment to maintaining instructional quality in geographically isolated school contexts.

The findings imply that Teachers-in-Charge demonstrate strong instructional leadership competence that supports effective teaching practices and learner engagement in schools without permanent school heads. Their ability to protect instructional time, support teacher professional development, and monitor curriculum implementation suggests that Teachers-in-Charge function as effective instructional leaders even within resource-limited and geographically isolated settings.

However, the moderate rating related to conducting meetings during instructional time indicates the need to further strengthen structured instructional supervision schedules that minimize disruptions while maximizing opportunities for collaborative professional dialogue. Providing targeted leadership training programs focusing on instructional supervision strategies and time management may further enhance the instructional leadership effectiveness of Teachers-in-Charge and contribute to improved student learning outcomes.

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
1. Encourage teachers to use instructional materials freely.	3.90	0.31	High
2. Organize and deliver the instructional materials to teachers.	3.80	0.41	High
3. Students have sufficient access to the instructional materials.	3.80	0.41	High
4. Teachers have sufficient access to instructional materials.	3.80	0.41	High
5. Recommend resources in areas in which teachers need.	3.80	0.41	High
6. Guide teachers in using instructional resources.	3.83	0.38	High
7. Take feedback on availability of the instructional resources.	3.67	0.48	High
8. Visit classes regularly to observe teaching and learning.	3.43	0.57	High
9. Physically available for instructional issues.	3.67	0.55	High
10. Personally attend co-curricular activities of the school.	3.70	0.47	High
11. Conduct meetings to discuss instructional matters.	3.73	0.45	High
12. Discuss with teachers the matters related to the instruction.	3.77	0.43	High
13. Visibly present in school for teachers and students.	3.77	0.43	High
14. Available for teachers' professional development.	3.80	0.41	High
15. Plan faculty meetings for professional development.	3.73	0.45	High
16. Arrange teachers' meetings to help them grow professionally.	3.80	0.41	High
17. Develop follow up plans for assessing professional development.	3.63	0.49	High
18. Encourage teachers to take steps to solve instructional issues.	3.70	0.47	High
19. Encourage teachers to improve their classroom practices.	3.73	0.45	High
20. Plan professional development opportunities according to needs.	3.73	0.45	High
21. Ensure that all students are present in the class during class time.	3.87	0.35	High
22. Protect classroom instructional time from outside interruptions.	3.83	0.38	High
23. Encourage all teachers to come to class well-prepared and in time.	3.87	0.35	High
24. Use class time of teachers for regular meetings.	2.90	1.09	Moderate
25. Make sure that students are not allowed in the office during class.	3.53	0.57	High
26. Solve issues related to discipline to maximize instructional time.	3.63	0.56	High
27. Meet teachers individually to discuss student progress issues.	3.63	0.56	High
28. Discuss students' results with teachers for curricular strengths.	3.73	0.45	High
29. Review students' work when evaluating classroom instruction.	3.60	0.50	High
30. Ask the teachers to send the students' progress reports to parents.	3.67	0.61	High
31. Provide public praise to those teachers who perform well.	3.77	0.43	High
32. Reinforce the teachers by providing staff meetings/newsletters/ memos.	3.77	0.43	High

33. Praise outstanding students on their achievement publicly.	3.73	0.45	High
34. Communicate students' performance in parent teacher meetings.	3.87	0.35	High
35. Provide verbal and written feedback to my teachers.	3.60	0.56	High
36. Ensure that teachers teach the required curriculum.	3.83	0.38	High
37. Encourage a lesson plan/log for making curriculum effective.	3.73	0.45	High
38. Encourage teachers to engage their students in activities.	3.90	0.31	High
39. Meet with teachers to get reports about curriculum implementation.	3.73	0.45	High
40. Students' marks provide information about curriculum implementation.	3.53	0.57	High
Overall Mean	3.71	0.17	High
<i>Note: Scale – 4.21-5.00 (Very High), 3.41-4.20 (High), 2.61-3.40 (Moderate), 1.81-2.60 (Low), 1.00-1.80 (Very Low)</i>			
Overall Mean	3.71	0.17	High
<i>Note: Scale – 4.21-5.00 (Very High), 3.41-4.20 (High), 2.61-3.40 (Moderate), 1.81-2.60 (Low), 1.00-1.80 (Very Low)</i>			

Table 2. Level of Instructional Leadership Competence of Teachers-in-Charge

Level of Students' Academic Performance

Table 3 portrays the level of students' academic performance in classes handled by Teachers-in-Charge across the participating schools. The results indicate that the overall academic performance of learners was Very Satisfactory (M = 87.04, SD = 2.19), based on the grading descriptors prescribed by Department of Education under DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015.

Among the 30 classes included in the study, 21 classes (70%) obtained a Very Satisfactory level of performance (M = 88.89, SD = 1.36), 4 classes (13.33%) achieved an Outstanding level (M = 91.00, SD = 1.41), while 5 classes (16.67%) recorded a Satisfactory level (M = 84.52, SD = 0.56). These findings indicate that the majority of learners performed above the satisfactory level, suggesting generally strong academic achievement among pupils under the supervision of Teachers-in-Charge.

The overall Very Satisfactory performance of learners suggests that schools led by Teachers-in-Charge are able to maintain stable instructional delivery and learning outcomes despite the absence of formally designated school heads. This finding reinforces the earlier results showing that Teachers-in-Charge demonstrated high administrative and instructional leadership competence, which may contribute to sustaining effective classroom environments and learner engagement. The findings support existing literature emphasizing that instructional leadership plays a critical role in shaping student achievement. According to Philip Hallinger (2011), school leaders influence learning outcomes by supporting teachers' instructional practices, monitoring curriculum implementation, and protecting instructional time. Similarly, Robinson et al. (2008) identified leadership practices related to teacher development and curriculum supervision as among the strongest predictors of student achievement gains.

Moreover, the presence of classes that achieved Outstanding performance indicates that even within geographically isolated school contexts, Teachers-in-Charge are capable of facilitating high-quality instructional environments that support advanced learner achievement. This aligns with Leithwood et al. (2008), who emphasized that leadership effectiveness contributes significantly to improved student outcomes, particularly when leaders actively support instructional improvement and collaborative teaching practices.

However, the presence of several classes within the Satisfactory performance level suggests that contextual factors such as geographic isolation, resource limitations, and teachers' dual-role responsibilities may still influence variability in student achievement across schools. These contextual realities are common in upland and remote educational settings where access to instructional resources and support systems may be constrained.

The findings imply that learners under the supervision of Teachers-in-Charge generally demonstrate strong academic performance despite the challenges associated with dual-role leadership structures in geographically isolated schools. This suggests that Teachers-in-Charge are able to sustain effective instructional environments that support positive learner outcomes. However, the variation in performance levels across classes highlights the importance of strengthening instructional supervision support, resource allocation, and leadership development programs for Teachers-in-Charge. Enhancing leadership training and providing additional institutional support mechanisms may further improve consistency in learner achievement across schools and help maximize the instructional impact of Teachers-in-Charge in remote educational contexts.

Descriptive Performance of Learners	N	Mean	SD
3 (Satisfactory)	5	84.52	0.56

4 (Very Satisfactory)	21	88.89	1.36
5 (Outstanding)	4	91.00	1.41
Total (Very Satisfactory)	30	87.04	2.19

Note: 90-100 (Outstanding); 85 – 89 (Very Satisfactory); 80 – 84 (Satisfactory)

Table 3. Level of Students' Academic Performance

Relationship Between Teachers-in-Charge Administrative Leadership Competence, Instructional Leadership Competence, and Students' Academic Performance

Table 4 presents the relationship between Teachers-in-Charge's administrative leadership competence, instructional leadership competence, and students' academic performance using Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient. The results revealed that administrative leadership competence was not significantly related to students' academic performance ($r = -0.092$, $p = 0.628$). Similarly, instructional leadership competence was not significantly related to students' academic performance ($r = -0.132$, $p = 0.486$). Both correlations indicate weak negative relationships and were statistically not significant at the 0.05 level, suggesting that variations in leadership competence among Teachers-in-Charge did not correspond to measurable differences in students' academic achievement within the sample.

These findings indicate that although Teachers-in-Charge demonstrated high levels of administrative and instructional leadership competence (as shown in Tables 1 and 2), such competencies did not translate into statistically significant improvements in students' academic performance in the present study. This result suggests that leadership competence alone may not directly influence learner achievement, particularly in geographically isolated school contexts where multiple external factors affect instructional delivery and student learning outcomes.

The absence of a significant relationship between leadership competence and student performance aligns with studies suggesting that the effect of school leadership on student achievement is often indirect rather than direct, operating through mediating variables such as teacher motivation, instructional quality, school climate, and availability of learning resources. According to Kenneth Leithwood et al. (2008), school leadership influences student learning primarily through its impact on teachers' working conditions and instructional practices rather than through immediate measurable effects on student achievement.

Similarly, Hallinger (2011) emphasized that instructional leadership contributes to improved academic outcomes indirectly by shaping teaching effectiveness, monitoring curriculum implementation, and supporting professional development. These leadership effects typically emerge over time and may not be immediately observable through short-term academic performance indicators such as class mean grades. Another possible explanation for the non-significant findings is the contextual nature of the study setting. Teachers-in-Charge in upland and geographically isolated schools often operate within constrained environments characterized by limited instructional resources, transportation challenges, and socio-economic barriers affecting learner participation and achievement. Such contextual variables may moderate or mask the influence of leadership competence on student outcomes. Research by Robinson et al. (2008) supports this interpretation, noting that leadership impact on achievement depends heavily on contextual conditions and the extent to which leaders are able to influence instructional processes directly.

Studies have shown that the effectiveness of instructional leadership often depends not only on the competencies of school leaders but also on external factors, including available resources, teacher motivation, and student-related variables (Orr, 2023; Parveen et al., 2022). As per Second Congressional Commission on Education report in 2025, nutritional status of school children such as stunting correlate with poor academic performance and directly impacting literacy rate (Cariasao, 2025). The present findings correspond with literature emphasizing the challenges of balancing teaching and leadership, where role strain, time management pressures, and conflicting priorities may dilute the direct impact of leadership on student outcomes (Bush et al., 2021; O'Donnell, 2023; Atywood, 2024). For example, the demands of administrative oversight can reduce the frequency of classroom observation, timely feedback, and individualized student support, potentially limiting the observable effect of teacher-in-charge on academic performance (Shahin et al., 2024; Marshall et al., 2022).

Furthermore, the dual-role responsibilities of Teachers-in-Charge—as both classroom teachers and acting school administrators—may distribute leadership attention across multiple operational demands, thereby reducing the direct observable influence of leadership competence on learners' academic performance. While leadership competence remains essential for maintaining school operations and supporting instructional processes, its measurable effect on academic outcomes may require sustained institutional support and longer implementation periods to become statistically evident.

The findings imply that although Teachers-in-Charge demonstrate strong administrative and instructional leadership competence, improvements in students' academic performance cannot be attributed solely to leadership competence within the present study context. This highlights the importance of considering additional influencing variables such as instructional resources, teacher workload, learner characteristics, and school environmental conditions when examining student achievement outcomes in geographically isolated schools.

Variables	r	p	Interpretation
Administrative Leadership Competence and Students' Academic Performance	-0.092	0.628	*NS, weak negative
Instructional Leadership Competence and Students' Academic Performance	-0.132	0.486	*NS, weak negative

Note. *r* = Pearson correlation coefficient; *p* = significance value. All correlations are not significant (NS) meaning $p > 0.05$. Correlation is significant if $p < .05$.

Table 4. Relationship Between Teachers-in-Charge Administrative Leadership Competence, Instructional Leadership Competence, and Students' Academic Performance

Conclusion and Recommendations

The findings of the study revealed that Teachers-in-Charge demonstrated high levels of administrative and instructional leadership competence, indicating their capability to effectively manage school operations and support instructional processes even in the absence of formally designated school heads. Their strong performance in administrative personal skills, leadership competence, instructional supervision, professional development support, and protection of instructional time reflects their adaptability and commitment to sustaining school functionality in geographically isolated settings. These results suggest that Teachers-in-Charge are able to assume leadership responsibilities beyond classroom instruction and contribute meaningfully to maintaining organizational stability and instructional continuity in their respective schools.

In terms of learners' outcomes, the results showed that students achieved an overall Very Satisfactory level of academic performance, indicating that teaching-learning processes remained effective despite contextual challenges and dual-role leadership structures. The presence of classes with Outstanding performance further suggests that Teachers-in-Charge are capable of fostering supportive instructional environments that promote positive learner achievement. However, variations in performance across classes highlight the influence of contextual factors such as limited resources, geographic isolation, and workload demands, which may affect consistency in academic outcomes across schools.

Despite the high levels of leadership competence observed among Teachers-in-Charge, the study found no significant relationship between leadership competence and students' academic performance, suggesting that leadership influence on achievement may be indirect and mediated by other school-related and learner-related variables. These findings emphasize the importance of strengthening institutional support systems, leadership development programs, instructional resources, and collaborative professional practices to enhance the effectiveness of Teachers-in-Charge in geographically isolated schools. Overall, the study underscores the critical role of Teachers-in-Charge as school-based leaders while highlighting the need for sustained structural support to maximize their impact on learner achievement and school improvement.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their gratitude to the Department of Education, Division of Aklan, District of Madalag and Aklan State University College of Teacher Education for the support.

Funding

This research received no external funding from any public, commercial, or not-for-profit funding agency, and no organization provided financial support for the conduct of the study, authorship, or publication of this article.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study; all data used were obtained from previously published sources as cited in the reference list.

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Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.